

Association Analysis of primary Liver Cancer based on Apriori Algorithm

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Abstract: This paper briefly describes the Apriori algorithm for primary liver cancer data, and then performs data preprocessing based on the characteristics of primary liver cancer patients, including data import and extraction, and embedding the algorithm into primary liver cancer. The implementation of clinical warning. After that, the Apriori algorithm is used to realize the association of the data association rules of primary liver cancer, and the internal valuable association rules are obtained, which provides suggestions for improving the doctor's remediation and prevention, so as to prevent the occurrence and reduction of primary liver cancer. The incidence of primary liver cancer has important practical significance.

Keywords: Apriori algorithm; primary liver cancer; Association rules; association analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

With the widespread use of hospital digital devices, the information capacity of medical databases is expanding. The development of database technology solves the problem of the efficiency of mass data storage and data retrieval, but it cannot change the phenomenon of “data explosion but lack of knowledge”[1]. How to make full use of these valuable medical information resources to provide scientific decision-making for the diagnosis and treatment of diseases and promote medical research has become the focus of attention

Primary liver cancer is one of the common malignant tumors in China, and the mortality rate of patients' accounts for the third place in malignant tumors. Primary liver cancer refers to malignant tumors that occur in hepatocytes or intrahepatic cholangiocarcinoma cells, most of which are hepatocellular carcinomas. The degree of malignancy is high and the metastasis is strong. The prognosis depends on the timely diagnosis and early treatment. The dynamics of alpha-fetoprotein. The combination of monitoring and multiple imaging examinations is an important means

of early diagnosis. The prognosis of the disease can only be roughly judged by the doctor's professional knowledge and experience, which has a negative impact on both doctors and patients. Because of the value of the data, there are few studies on primary liver cancer at home and abroad, and there is no corresponding model to analyze the degree of association between the indicators of the patients. Even the continuous advancement of high-tech cannot predict the liver cancer. Occurrence, in order to better solve the health problems people care about, try to apply the correlation algorithm to the analysis of primary liver cancer data, in order to analyze the impact of different indicators on the disease by computer, explore the potential association, help control The occurrence of primary liver cancer disease.

II. RESEARCH STATUS AT HOOME AND ABROAD

Association rules, decision trees, artificial neural networks, etc. are commonly used data mining algorithms. Association rule analysis is a very important tool in the field of data mining and one of the most mature methods. The Apriori algorithm was first proposed by Agralwal and Srikant in 1993. It is

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currently recognized as one of the more efficient association rule algorithms. The algorithm has good practicability after optimization for different industry characteristics. Similarly, the optimized Apriori algorithm is also suitable for correlation studies in diseases with high prevalence such as liver cancer. Experts have accumulated a large amount of data in the practice of diagnosis and treatment, which contains diseases, syndromes, dialectical diagnosis thinking and skills, and prescriptions. Important data information on medications, treatment methods, evolution of symptoms and development trends. The amount of data is large, the data structure is complex, and the data is ambiguous. How to find the law from these data and achieve accurate prevention is a current research direction.

The purpose of association analysis is to find the connections and laws between things and discover the relationship between them. There are more and more algorithms for mining association rules, but Kamber [1] and Liu Meiling [2] both propose that Apriori algorithm is the core algorithm of simple association rule technology. Apriori algorithm includes two parts: one is to generate frequent itemsets, frequently The item set is the item set whose frequency of occurrence is greater than the specified minimum support. The second is to generate strong association rules based on the frequent itemsets generated in the previous step. The strong association rule is the rule that meets the specified minimum support and minimum confidence. The Apriori algorithm connects the frequent itemsets generated in the previous step to itself every time the candidate set is generated [3]. It is usually used to mine the database of association rules. The scale is very large, so the extra is added in the invisible. The connection overhead reduces the execution efficiency of the algorithm.

At present, there are many methods for improving the efficiency of Apriori algorithm. The literature [4-6] contains the keywords such as segmentation and grouping in the improvement of the algorithm, but all of them are considered from the perspective of support segmentation to improve the efficiency of the algorithm. In this paper, based on the characteristics of primary liver cancer diagnosis and treatment data, it is proposed to use the Apriori algorithm based on the Apriori algorithm to judge the specific characteristics of the primary liver cancer, and then use the changes in the

characteristics to find There is a trend and magnitude of the characteristic changes associated with the play.

III. DATA MINING BASED ON ASSOCIATION RULES

In practical applications, how to effectively define frequent and associated? Support and Confidence are generally used to filter useful rules. In order to analyze the relationship between the disease factors caused by primary liver cancer, the association rules in data mining are used to analyze the corresponding relationship, and the relationship between features and characteristics is found out, which is convenient for doctors to be more targeted in practical work. Check for changes in specific characteristics, reduce the incidence of primary liver cancer, and prevent early treatment in advance.

Fig 1: Steps for mining association rules.

A. Steps for mining association rules:

- Find out all the frequent itemsets existing in the dataset, that is, find those itemsets whose support degree is not less than a given support threshold.
- A strong association rule is generated on the basis of a frequent item set, that is, an association rule whose support degree and confidence are respectively greater than or equal to a given support degree threshold and a confidence threshold are generated.

B. Association Rules

Let I be a set of data items, and D is a data set associated with it. In D , each transaction T is a non-empty subset of I , that is $T \subset I$, each transaction has a corresponding identification number, called TID. If A and B are the project sets, and $A \cap B = \emptyset$, the support degree of the association rule $A \Rightarrow B$ is defined as the probability that the transaction in D contains both A and B is called $P(A \cup B)$, and the confidence is that the

transaction in D already contains A. It also contains the percentage of B, that is, the conditional probability is $P(B|A)$.

$$\text{Support}(A \Rightarrow B) = P(A \cup B) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Confidence}(A \Rightarrow B) = P(B|A) \quad (2)$$

A set of items with a support greater than the minimum support is called a frequent item set. When the association rule meets the requirements of the minimum support threshold and the minimum confidence threshold at the same time, the association rule is called a strong association rule, and vice versa is a weak association rule. The above threshold needs to be set according to data mining. For ease of calculation, the values of support and confidence are generally expressed as values between 0 and 100% instead of values between 0 and 1.0 [7].

C. Frequent Itemsets

Apriori algorithm is a classic algorithm in association rule data mining. The algorithm generates frequent itemsets required by Boolean association rules by mining data, and the core of the association rule mining algorithm is to find frequent itemsets. The following steps are required to find frequent itemsets:

- The candidate set C1 is generated from the data set (1 indicates that there is only one data item for each candidate); then C1 passes the support degree filtering to generate the frequent item set L1 (1 means that each frequent item has only one data item).
- Splicing the data items of L1 into C2.
- Starting from candidate set C2, L2 is generated by support degree filtering. L2 is stitched into candidate set C3 according to the Apriori principle; C3 generates L3 by support filtering until there is only one or no data item in Lk.

The algorithm's loop process: Search the database layer by layer to calculate the support of the candidate set, compare it with the minimum support, find the largest item set in the k dimension, so the complexity of the algorithm increases exponentially. Therefore, if there are n items, then there are 2^n possible frequent itemsets, which constitute the possible solution space on item set I [8]. Figure 2 depicts the operation of finding frequent itemsets in a data set.

D. Apriori Algorithm

As a classic frequent item set mining algorithm for generating Boolean association rules, Apriori algorithm is based on the iterative method of layer-by-layer search. It mainly mines valuable association rules from static data information. The general idea is as follows: The database is scanned for the first time, and all individual project support is counted. Items that are not less than the given minimum support are grouped into frequent itemsets L1. Then scan the database repeatedly and recursively get the last frequent itemsets.

It can be simplified into the following three steps:

- (1) Connection step: Connect (k-1) - frequent item set to generate k-item candidate set.

Join condition: The first (k-2) terms of the 2 (k-1) terms are equal and the (k-1)th item of the 1st (k-1)th item set is compared to the 2nd (k-1) item set. The (k-1)th item is small.

- (2) Deletion step: Pruning the k-term candidate set by using the important properties of the Apriori algorithm.

Pruning rule: If any (k-1) item subset of a k-term candidate set does not belong to the (k-1)-term frequent set L, the candidate set k-item set may be deleted.

- (3) Counting step: Scan the transaction database and accumulate the number of occurrences of the k-item candidate set in the database

Counting method: If the transaction record contains the candidate set, the number of occurrences of the candidate set is increased by one. A k-term frequent set is then generated based on a given minimum support threshold. The flow chart is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Apriori algorithm flow chart

IV. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

A. Arrangement Data collection and Data Organization

The experimental data were from the Eastern Hepatobiliary Hospital of the Second Military Medical University. There were three types of malignant tumors, benign lesions and normal. There were 588 data sets, including malignant tumors: 246 groups, benign lesions: 149 groups, and normal groups: 193 groups.

There are too many missing values in the data itself, and it is not easy to conduct correlation analysis. With

the help of professionals, in addition to many irrelevant indicators, each case includes 40 anonymous indicators. Due to privacy protection, the sample set has many missing values. It is proposed to set the value of the missing value to 0 in order to make correlation analysis and better observe the relationship between features and features.

B. Visualization of Results

The basic idea of data visualization technology is to represent each data item in the database as a single primitive element. In the data of primary liver cancer, according to the association rule, the Apriori algorithm is used to represent each attribute value of the patient in the form of multidimensional data. Observe data from different dimensions, conduct more in-depth observation and analysis of the data, and discover potential rules between features. Figure 4 shows the analysis of the characteristics of primary liver cancer based on the Apriori algorithm.

Fig 4: Experimental result

It can be clearly seen from the figure that there is a certain degree of correlation between the 40 features. According to the positive and negative related content, the importance of the specific features can be found. The results of association rule mining are often used to assist in data analysis and decision making. Good effectiveness plays an important role in its development

and application. Among them, the mining of frequent itemsets and the resulting association rules are often closer to reality. Through the analysis of association rules, this paper introduces frequent itemsets and degree of association, optimizes the generation process and result set, reduces the generation of redundant and false rules, and ensures correlation and precision. Starting from a single feature, we can see the degree of association with the other 39 features, combined with the comparison, and screen out the negative correlation features, while in the figure v4, v5, v11, v12, v13, v14, v25, v26 several features such as v27 and v28 are more positively correlated with other features. It can be concluded that the characteristics are fed back to the hospital, and the corresponding indicators are found to control the changes of the patients in these characteristics and track. The trend of these related indicators is an important theory for future medical practitioners to prevent the prevalence of primary liver cancer.

Acknowledgment

In this paper, we try to apply Apriori algorithm to the medical field, and we can find the correlation between features and features in primary hepatocellular carcinoma. According to the characteristics of Apriori algorithm, we can clearly depict the correlation degree between a single feature and other features of primary hepatocellular carcinoma, which is the comparison of different correlation algorithms in the later stage. It left a foundation. It further shows that the increasingly perfect application of big data technology in the medical field is an indispensable trend, which deserves more in-depth exploration and research.

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